

The choice of spatial scale in epidemiological research studies about tuberculosis in cities: a review protocol

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Contributions to the review protocol (in line with the CRediT (<https://credit.niso.org/>) taxonomy): conceptualization (SD, CN, LO, KV, VV), methodology (CN, LO, KP, KV, VV), funding acquisition (LO, VV, KV), project administration (VV), supervision (LO, KP, KV), writing – original draft (VV), writing – review and editing (SD, CN, LO, KP, KV)

Registration

We register the present protocol on the Zenodo platform (<https://zenodo.org/>). In that way, the document gets a Digital Object Identifier (DOI). Although this is not a systematic review, we have used the PRISMA-P guidelines (preferred reporting items for systematic review and meta-analysis protocols) to structure this protocol(1).

Amendments

This is the first version of the protocol (1.0), dated 01 June 2025. We will document any important amendments in new versions of the protocol, which we will also register in Zenodo.

Support

This study builds further on a thesis project developed in the framework of a Master of Science in Public Health (MPH) at the Institute of Tropical Medicine in Antwerp, Belgium. Victor Vega was the MPH thesis candidate; he received a scholarship from the Belgian Directorate-general for Development Cooperation and Humanitarian Aid (DGD) for the duration of the MPH course. Kristien Verdonck acted as the thesis coach. The MPH thesis was defended in July 2024(2). The present scoping review project does not only update the MPH thesis project; it also involves a larger and more diverse team of reviewers. The funder of the MPH scholarship had no role in the writing of this review protocol or in the decision to submit it for registration.

Introduction

Health inequities manifest in spatially dependent ways. One way to study them is through disaggregation of health-related information by geographical location, beyond national level, an approach that has been recognised as a step forward towards ensuring the “Leave no one behind” promise in the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development(3). Health-related information encompasses population health data, healthcare data, and health-related data from other sectors, such as, for example, socio-economic characteristics like education level or poverty, and characteristics of the living space like housing conditions(4). This information is often managed through health information systems which, if robust enough, allow the generation of evidence to inform policymaking.

In the past two decades, **epidemiological analyses of spatial data have resurged in the field of public health**. This could be linked to advancements in geographic information systems (GIS), expanded access to (georeferenced) satellite imagery, and increased availability of routine health data including spatial identifiers. Moreover, there is a growing momentum around the view that space is not just a passive background, but a factor that dynamically interacts with health outcomes.

We intend to explore how spatial public health and related methodological developments translate into epidemiological research practices. In the present review, we use one case, namely the **geographical distribution of the burden of tuberculosis in cities**. We focus on tuberculosis in cities because it is relatively common; its distribution is known to be heterogeneous; the number of publications on this topic is moderate; the pathogenesis of tuberculosis comprises different stages with varying underlying processes and factors; and we have some expertise in this area. In addition, TB is known to be linked to spatial characteristics that define its transmission dynamics. More specifically, we set out to assess **how researchers choose and justify the spatial scale** at which they study and report on tuberculosis in cities. Different scales can reveal or mask heterogeneity, thereby shaping the way inequities are understood, measured and addressed, or neglected altogether, and influencing the precision of burden estimates.

We **anticipate** that we will find that (1) the number of publications reporting on the spatial distribution of urban tuberculosis has increased in recent years; (2) research approaches are evolving and not yet established, and (3) the choice of scale is often determined by the availability of routine data.

Objective

Explore which spatial scales have been used in the academic literature about tuberculosis in cities and assess which arguments the authors used to justify their choice of scale. For the purpose of this review, we define spatial scales as **the spatial dimensions at which entities, patterns, and processes are observed and characterised**.

Methods

Theoretical framework

We developed a theoretical framework, summarised in Figure 1, based on literature from the geography field(2). The aim of this framework is to capture overlaps between spatial scale, health phenomena of interest and health-related data and policy. In this review, we will use this framework as an analytical tool to guide the identification and classification of the spatial scales found in the included papers as well as the rationale behind their selection. The components of the framework are described below.

Figure 1 Framework on spatial scales and their relationship with health, health-related data, and policy(2)

Spatial scales

In the geography literature, different types of spatial scales have been identified: process scale, geographical scale, observation scale, and policy scale. These types of spatial scales are incorporated in the framework (Figure 1) and explained below.

Process scale

Infectious diseases and their determinants entail complex processes involving the host, the infectious agent, the reservoirs, the vectors and the environment. The process scale answers the question: Where does the health-related process (susceptibility; subclinical disease; clinical disease; recovery, disability, or death) manifest?

Defining the process scale for some health-related processes can be challenging or even impossible because they are volatile or they occur at scales that are not visible enough to be positioned in space (e.g. tuberculosis infection outside the household).

Geographical scale

Attempts to measure the phenomena of interest result in data that has spatial characteristics. For this purpose, a question is proposed: which is the geographical space covered by the data? The total area for which data is available defines the geographical scale.

Observation scale

Within the geographical scale, additional spatial units can be compared using the data. The size of these units defines the observation scales. The choice of the observation scale is usually linked with the purpose and setting of data collection (e.g. quantitative and/or qualitative research, routine disease surveillance or health system data, or public demographic and health surveys). Data collection also depends on the availability of resources and on socio-political arguments. Administrative units and boundaries are commonly used for benchmarking purposes and subsequently used as secondary data for research. However, the advent of modern geographical information systems (GIS) techniques has increased the access to fine-scale data and led to more varied geographical demarcations.

Policy scale

This scale is determined by the space that is administered by policy. Ideally, policy decisions should be based on data that are tailored to the phenomenon of interest and that are able to intervene at a scale that fits within the administrative boundary. Some examples include: cities, districts, multistorey and individual houses.

Some considerations of the other components of the framework include:

Health phenomena of interest

In this framework, the health phenomena of interest include processes related to a disease and its determinants. Those processes are spatial, meaning that they occur in specific locations that can be identified in space.

Data

The data component of the framework includes routine surveillance health data, population-level survey data, research data, and publicly available data. Using this data, different indicators can be built to quantify the frequency of the health phenomena of interest and related measures of association.

Policy

The policy component in the framework refers to the interventions that address the health phenomena either directly or through their determinants. In this review, we focus on the spatial dimension; i.e., where the policy interventions take place.

Study design

We adopt a scoping review approach as it is well suited for mapping research methodologies(5).

Review question

The Population/Concept/Context (PCC) framework(6) applied to this review is summarised in Box 1.

Box 1 Population/Concept/Context framework

Population: People affected by tuberculosis
Concept: Selection of spatial scale
Context: Urban settings

The question for this review is:

Which spatial scales have been used in research about tuberculosis in urban settings and how have researchers explained their choice of spatial scale?

Eligibility criteria

The eligibility criteria are defined in line with the components of the PCC framework and the type of sources of evidence.

Population

This review will include studies that measure TB-related outcomes in people affected by TB, defined, according to the Global Tuberculosis Dictionary(7), as “*those with tuberculosis or who previously had tuberculosis, as well as their caregivers and immediate family members*”. The rationale of including a broad population group is to ensure comprehensive coverage of the different stages of the disease to be then linked with the corresponding spatial scales according to the proposed framework.

Concept

This review will address the concept of spatial scale in epidemiology and public health. Based on the definitions of the types of scales, studies that involve the selection of a spatial scale, with the intention to compare TB-related outcomes across geographical areas within a city will be included.

Context

The context for this review will be limited to urban settings, with city as maximum geographical scale and any lower scale data as observational scale. If higher-level geographical scale (country, province, regions, etc.) or combinations of different types of settings (rural and urban) are reported, the record will be included if it is possible to extract data within the city scale.

Type of sources of evidence

This scoping review will focus on methodologies adopted in scientific literature. It will only include peer-reviewed primary research publications. Experimental and observational studies will be eligible. Sources of evidence will be included if they document TB-related outcomes by means of incidence, prevalence and/or counts. There will be no *a priori* restrictions on language and date of publication.

Review papers, opinion and viewpoints will not be included in the review but considered, if relevant, for the discussion. Studies conducted at the individual scale will be excluded.

Search strategy

We have developed a search strategy based on the elements of the PCC framework. The search string combines text words related to tuberculosis, spatial scales, and urban settings. MEDLINE/PubMed and, to capture Latin American literature, also Scientific Electronic Library Online (SciELO) are used as the primary databases for identifying sources of evidence. In addition, we plan to review the first 100 records ranked by relevance in both OpenAlex and ITM's EBSCO Discovery Service (EDS), totaling 200 records. These two scholarly search platforms may identify relevant sources of evidence missed by MEDLINE/PubMed and SciELO, due to limitations in journal coverage or challenges with search term matching.. The search strategy for MEDLINE/PubMed uses medical subject headings (MeSH) terms to ensure that literature categorised under related subdomains is also captured. The full preliminary search strategy is provided below:

PubMed/Medline search syntax

#1	"tuberculosis"[Title/Abstract] OR "tuberculosis"[MeSH Terms] OR "mycobacterium tuberculosis"[Title/Abstract]
#2	"spatial analysis"[MeSH Terms] OR "geographic mapping"[MeSH Terms] OR "spatial scale"[Title/Abstract] OR "geographical scale"[Title/Abstract] OR "spatial resolution"[Title/Abstract] OR "spatial granularity"[Title/Abstract] OR "spatial heterogeneity"[Title/Abstract] OR "scale selection"[Title/Abstract]
#3	"urban"[Title/Abstract] OR "city"[Title/Abstract]
#4	#2 OR "mapping"[Title/Abstract]
#5	#1 AND #2
#6	#1 AND #4 AND #3
#7	#5 OR #6

Scientific Electronic Library Online (SciELO) syntax

#1	tuberculosis
#2	escala OR análisis espacial OR heterogeneidad OR mapa
#3	ciudad OR urban*
#4	#1 AND #2 AND #3

OpenAlex

#1	tuberculosis
#2	spatial scale
#3	#1 AND #2

EBSCO Discovery Service (EDS) at ITM library

	(tuberculosis AND spatial AND scale)
OR	(tuberculosis AND spatial AND (city OR urban))

Selection of sources of evidence

We will collect all sources of evidence in the Covidence platform and remove any duplicates identified during the import process. Two reviewers will independently screen titles and abstracts, then review full-text reports to determine eligibility, and record reasons for exclusion. We will summarise the search and selection process in a flow diagram, in line with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analyses extension for scoping review (PRISMA-ScR)(8,9).

Data charting process

A data extraction form will be built in Covidence to facilitate consistent data charting. One reviewer will extract data; another reviewer will check the extracted data and contrast it, where possible and relevant, with data extracted previously as part of the initial Master thesis.

Data items

A first set of data items will cover characteristics of the publication such as principal author and year of publication. A second set is related to study setting and methods: country, city, WHO region, epidemiological design, study period, indicators used, data sources, type of data (aggregated or case-based), spatial analysis techniques, type of spatial data used, and whether spatial-temporal analysis was conducted. The third set of data items targets the core of this review, i.e. the spatial scales. We will register the spatial scales used in the analysis and whether or not these scales were designed by the investigators. To characterise the spatial scales, information on population size, area and number of units within the city will be also extracted. Definitions of and justifications for the observation scale will be extracted verbatim, as provided by the authors.

Critical appraisal of individual sources of evidence

This scoping review will not include an appraisal of risk of bias using standard tools, as these are designed to evaluate bias in outcome measures, which are not the focus of this review. Instead, the core theme of the review is methodological and it involves an in-depth assessment of a specific component of the methods used in the included studies.

Data analysis and presentation of results

To ensure that this review is informed by different disciplinary perspectives, researchers with diverse backgrounds (epidemiology, urbanism, social sciences) will participate in the review process, from search and selection up to analysis and synthesis.

Study characteristics will be summarised in a table. The scales used will be characterised in terms of population, area, and number of units in the study setting.

The authors' justifications for their choice of scale will be aligned to the three components of the framework: process, data and policy.

1. Process: authors selected the scale based on criteria related to the disease mechanism.
2. Data: the scale was determined by considerations related to characteristics of the data.
3. Policy: the scale was determined by considerations about the scale at which a specific TB prevention or control intervention could be implemented.

As authors can give more than one justification for their choice of scale, these three categories are not mutually exclusive. Overlaps will be illustrated in a Venn diagram in the results section.

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